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Gasdermin E activation in Crohn's Disease.

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Gasdermins are transcriptional products of non-canonical inflammasomes and expressed in differentiated epithelial cell types according to cell death activation status and developmental stage. We found induction of GSDME in the hematopoietic compartment in humans with Crohn's Disease. The data provide evidence indicating activation of pyroptosis in Crohn's Disease (1).

Citations

1. Zhou, B., Jiang, Z.H., Dai, M.R., Ai, Y.L., Xiao, L., Zhong, C.Q., Wu, L.Z., Chen, Q.T., Chen, H.Z. and Wu, Q., 2024. Full-length GSDME mediates pyroptosis independent from cleavage. Nature Cell Biology, 26(9), pp.1545-1557.

GSE186507